

An Examination Of Indian Language Machine Translation Tools

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Abstract

Although there has been work in the field of machine translation for a few decades, the promising translation work started in the early 1990s as a result of cutting-edge research in artificial intelligence and computational linguistics. India is a multilingual and multicultural nation with a population of over 1.25 billion people and 22 legally recognised languages that use 12 distinct scripts. This makes an automated machine translation system for English to Indian languages and among Indian languages necessary so that people can communicate in their native tongue. In India and other countries, wide varieties of practical machine translation systems have been created or are being worked on. The study focuses on several methods utilised in the creation of machine translation systems and briefly describes some of them.

Keywords: Machine Translation, Machine Translation Tools.

Introduction

Since India is a sizable multilingual nation with several regional languages, machine translation is necessary for effective communication. But in India, the earliest initiatives date back to the mid- and early-'90s[1]. The spoken language in India changes every 100 kilometres. In addition to the 2000 or so dialects that are spoken by various communities throughout India, there are 22 official languages. Most Indian states utilise English and Hindi for official correspondence. While the official work of the Union government is conducted in English and/or Hindi, the state governments in India primarily conduct their official business in their own regional languages. All of the Union government's official reports and papers are available in Hindi, English, or both languages. Regional language editions of several newspapers are also available. It takes a lot of time and money to hand translates these materials. In order to improve communication between states and the Union governments and information sharing among the people of various states who speak various regional languages, it is necessary to build effective machine translation (hence referred to as MT) systems to handle all these challenges. A large number of scholars, institutions, and research groups in India have begun working on MT systems for English to Indian languages and have been successful in achieving extremely good outcomes among Indian languages. The Government of India has made the decision to give Language

Technology for Indian languages more focus during the VIIIth Plan and to start a programme that would place an emphasis on quality, national relevance, and participation of traditional knowledge and R & D efforts in the field of information processing in Indian languages.

Indian Machine Translation Tools Based On Different Techniques

When a language is translated into another with the aid of a computing device, this is known as machine translation. There are various machine translation system as it is shown below.

Rule Based Machine Translation System Direct Machine Translation Tool Anusaaraka

The 1995-started Anusaaraka project is being managed by IIIT Hyderabad. One of the goals of the study was to perform MT between two Indian languages. The Ministry of Information Technology, Government of India, Technology Development for Indian Languages (TDIL), and Satyam Computers Private Limited are funding the initiative. The target language is Hindi, while the source languages are other indian languages, including bengali, punjabi, telugu, etc. The tool has been tested mostly for translating children's stories, despite not being domain-specific [2].

Transfer-Based Machine Translation Systems

Mantra

For the protection of knowledge, Bharati invented the English to Hindi MT system known as Mantra on 1997. Using this

technique, the text that is available in one Indian language may be accessed in another Indian language. For executing the analysis of the input English text, it makes use of a super tagger based on XTAG and a light dependency analyzer created at the University of Pennsylvania. It uses unique methods of load distribution between man and machine. For a given input, the system generates a number of outputs. Using a complete parser and a multilingual dictionary, the output is based on the most thorough examination of the English input text[3].

Mantra-MT

A machine-aided translation tool was created by Hemant Darbari and Mahendra Kumar Pandey (MANTRA) in 1999. A specialised area of personal administration, such as gazette notices, office orders, office memoranda, and circulars, is translated from English to Hindi using this programme. In its early iteration, the system was tested for the translation from English to Hindi of official documents issued by the federal government, such as appointment letters, notifications, and circulars. It employs the Tree Adjoining Grammar (TAG) formalism created by the University of Pennsylvania as well as Lexicalized Tree Adjoining Grammar (LTAG).

The Rajya Sabha Secretariat, India's Upper House of Parliament, established the technology, which is used to interpret legislative processes like Bulletin. The English-Bengali, English-Telugu, English-Gujarati, and Hindi-English language pairings, as well as those between Indian languages like Hindi-Bengali and Hindi-Marathi, may all use this method. The Mantra technique is universal, but the generated vocabulary and grammatical rules were only applicable to the domain's sub-language [3][4].

MAT

Using a morphological analyzer and generator for Kannada, Murthy K built a machine-assisted translation system for translating English texts into Kannada in 2002. The Universal Clause Structure Grammar (UCSG) parser analyses the English input phrase and produces the number, type, and connections between the various clauses and word groups. The

bilingual dictionary is used to find the appropriate equivalent in the target language for each term. The target language sentence is then created by arranging the clauses and word groupings in the proper linear order in accordance with the grammar of the target language. To change the translated text, a post-editing tool is offered. The accuracy of the MAT System 1.0 was around 40–60% when completely automated. Government circulars were the system's primary focus [5].

Shakti

In 2003 a system that translates English into any Indian language using a straightforward system architecture has been created by Bharati, R Moona, P Reddy, B Sankar, D M Sharma, and R Sangal. It blends a statistical technique with language rule-based approach. There are several different modules that make up the system. The remaining nine modules are used to create the target Indian language, the remaining 24 modules are used to conduct multilingual activities, and the last nine modules are used to analyse the source language (English) [6].

OMTrans

Using the syntax and semantics of the source and target languages, Mohanty S. and Balabantaray R. C. created a system that translates text from English to Oriya in 2004. This system also handles Word Sense Disambiguation (WSD). The object-oriented methodology is used in the design and development of OMTrans [7].

MaTra

In 2004 and 2006 system combining a transfer-based method and a structured representation in the form of frames has been created by Ananthakrishnan R, Kavitha M, Hegde J J, Chandra Shekhar, Ritesh Shah, Sawani Bade, and Sasikumar M. In order to clear up ambiguity, it also employs heuristics. News, yearly reports, and technical terms are under the purview of the system [8].

Sampark

The Department of Electronics and Information Technology, the government of India, supported the development of a multipart machine translation system for Indian Language to India Language Machine Translation (ILMT) by a consortium of 11 Indian academic institutions in 2009. It blends machine learning with computational

paninian grammar (CPG) to analyse language. It is created by combining statistical machine learning with both conventional rule-based and dictionary-based methods. For nine Indian languages, this group has created language technology, resulting in machine translation for 18 Indian language pairings [9].

Interlingua Machine Translation Systems

Anglabharti

In 2001 In order to translate English into Indian languages, R M K Sinha, R Jain, and A Jain created a machine translation system. A pseudo-interlingua technique is used in its development. Since more than one Indian language can now be translated from English using the same system, there is no longer a need to create separate translation software for each Indian language. This is thanks to the interlingua technique. One time only is the analysis of English as the source language performed, and the intermediate structure, known as PLIL, is produced (Pseudo Lingua for Indian Languages). A text-generation mechanism is used to translate the PLIL into each Indian language. Text generation takes 30% less work than PLIL creation, which takes 70% more work. New English to Indian language translation technology only requires an extra 30% of effort.

Anglahindi

In 2003 Angla Hindi was developed which is a variation of the English to Hindi Machine-Aided Translation System known as Angla Bharti MT System, which was created by R M K Sinha and Jain A for English to Indian languages. It utilises all of AnglaBharti's modules as well as an abstracted example-base for translating often used noun and verb phrases. 90% of the translation is accurate

Corpus Based Machine Translation

Example Based Machine Translation (EBMT) Systems

ANUBAAD

A machine translation (MT) system that translates news headlines from English to Bengali using an example-based method was created in 2004 by Bandyopadhyay S. The algorithm first looks for an exact match in the direct example base for an English news headline it has been provided as input. In the event that a match is discovered, the Bengali

headline from the example-base is generated as output. In the event that a match is unsuccessful, the headline is tagged, and the tagged headline is then looked up in the Generalized Tagged example-base. If a match is discovered in the Generalized Tagged Example-Base, the Bengali headline must be produced following the proper synthesis. The target translation will be produced using the Phrasal example-base if a match cannot be identified. Using a heuristic translation if the headline still cannot be translated [11].

Vaasaanubaada

In 2002 automatic machine translation system for Bengali-Assamese news texts was created by Vijayanand K, Choudhury S I, and Ratna P utilising the Example Based Machine Translation (EBMT) method. It involves sentence-level Bengali-Assamese machine translation for Bengali text. It comprises both preprocessing and postprocessing activities. The genuine cases were fed into the bilingual corpus manually and it was manually aligned. For improved translation quality, longer phrases are broken up at punctuation marks. In Example-Base, backtracking is employed when a precise match cannot be identified at the sentence or fragment level, and more sentence fragmentation is performed[12].

Shiva And Shakti

In 2003 both the MT system "Shiva" and the system "Shakti" were created utilising a combination of rule-based and statistical methodologies. The Shakti system can quickly create machine translation systems for new languages, and it now supports three target languages including Hindi, Marathi, and Telugu. The two machine translation programmes from English to Hindi, dubbed Shiva and Shakti, were created in collaboration between Carneige Mellon University in the United States, the International Institute of Information Technology in Hyderabad, and the Indian Institute of Science in Bangalore, India. The method is used to translate English statements into the proper Indian language for the intended audience. The statistical technique aims to infer or exploit linguistic information, and the rules employed for target language production are mostly linguistic in character. Some modules also make use of semantic data.

Anglabharti-Ii

In 2004 a generalised example-base (GEB) strategy for hybridization was proposed by R M K Sinha in addition to a Raw Example-Base approach (REB). The rule-based system can be difficult to change during the development phase and may provide unpredictable outcomes; instead, the example-base method is expanded interactively by enhancing the rule-base basis. Before calling upon the rule-base during real usage, the system initially tries to find a match in REB and GEB. Along with generic and conditional multi-word expressions, named-entities are also recognised, and automatic pre-editing and paraphrase are also provided. Additionally, it includes the modules needed to automate post-editing with an error-analysis and statistical language model. Using the automated pre-editing module, the input sentence is changed or paraphrased into a format that may be readily translated. Automatic pre-editing may even.

Statistical Machine Translation Systems Shakti

A MT system called as shakti was developed in 2003 that translates English text into any Indian language with a straightforward system architecture was created by Bharati, R Moona, P Reddy, B Sankar, D M Sharma, and R Sangal. It blends a statistical technique with language rule-based approach. 69 unique modules make up the system. The remaining nine modules are used to create the target Indian language, the remaining 24 modules are used to conduct multilingual activities, and the last nine modules are used to analyse the source language (English).

English to Indian Languages MT System (E-ILMT)

A MT system for English is developed in 2006 to Indian languages in the tourism and healthcare industries are called the EILMT. A group of nine institutions, including C-DAC Mumbai, IISc Bangalore, IIIT Hyderabad, C-DAC Pune, IIT Mumbai, Jadavpur University Kolkata, IIIT Allahabad, Utkal University Bangalore, Amrita University Coimbatore, and Banasthali Vidyapeeth, Banasthali, are responsible for its development. The Department of Information Technology,

MCIT, Government of India, is funding the initiative. To provide statistical models and materials for a statistical MT (SMT) system from English to Hindi, Marathi, and Bengali is the responsibility of C-DAC Mumbai.

Neural Machine Translation

The goal of machine translation (MT) is to close the communication gap between speakers of different languages. The job of the machine translation (MT) mechanism is to automatically translate between pairs of various natural languages; Neural Machine Translation (NMT) is gaining popularity since it provides good translation accuracy in cases when context analysis and fluent translation are used. In this study, two alternative NMT systems—NMT 1, which uses an attention model based on Long Short Term Memory (LSTM), and NMT-2, which uses a transformer model—are used for English to Hindi translation. Utilizing the Bilingual Evaluation Understudy (BLEU) measure, system results are assessed. The average BLEU scores for the NMT-1 and NMT-2 systems are 35.89 (Test-Set 1), 19.91 (Test-Set 2), and 34.42 (Test-Set 1), respectively. The outcomes indicate improved performance.

Hybrid Machine Translation

Using hybridised strategies including phrase-based translation, word alignment, and a language model, this study provides a machine translation system from Hindi to Malayalam with a focus on transition probability computation. The accuracy rate for this document is 90.725 percent [13].

In this work, the author provides an MTS from Sanskrit to English using a hybridised form of rule-based and direct machine translation. The suggested system made use of two bilingual Sanskrit-English dictionaries, a tagged Sanskrit corpus, a Sanskrit analysis rule foundation, and an ELGR base. The proposed system evaluated using Python's Natural Language Toolkit API obtained a BLEU score of 0.7606 [14].

Conclusions

A focus was placed on the creation of Machine translation Tools for both non-Indian languages and Indian languages in this paper's longitudinal and latitudinal description of MT approaches and its tools. Our investigation revealed that practically all of the MT systems for Indian languages

now in use are based on rule-based, hybrid, and statistical techniques. The majority of the MT systems and tools for Indian languages that have been created have used a rule-based, statistical, neural based and hybrid system.

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